

Preparing the Research & Innovation Core for Mission Ocean, Seas & Waters

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Roadmap to success for future LH projects:
Solutions to better address regulatory barriers and create enablers

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Executive Summary

This report examines the potential enablers and barriers, in terms of policy and regulation, for the large-scale implementation of innovative solutions within the Mission Ocean & Waters. Focusing on technologies and solutions currently in the development or pilot phase, the aim of this report is to shed light on the landscape of policy, regulation, and the associated challenges faced by innovators in the field and to bring forward solutions and recommendations.

To achieve this, a top-down approach was used, compiling 77 policies and regulations, linked to these technological innovations into a heatmap. This heatmap thus gives a clear overview of the currently relevant policy documents and instantly shows how closely they are linked to the specific objectives. At the same time, it is also set up as a living document capable of incorporating new developments as they arise.

The heatmap provided the framework for a bottom-up approach: 16 semi-structured interviews with innovators and researchers were conducted between June and October 2023 to gather their experiences in developing and deploying Mission-related innovations, supplemented by surveys sent out in collaboration with the PREP4BLUE partners.

From this information, respectively eight and seven higher-level barriers and enablers were distilled. Where possible, these barriers and enablers are illustrated in the report with practical examples or regional regulations are cited as sources of inspiration. One of the barriers for example is the disparity of policy implementation and adoption, where marine spatial planning and the port reception facilities are put forward as practical examples. One example of the enablers is the implementation of new technologies as result of the adoption of certain regulations, for which the Danish Mussel Policy is a good case study.

Finally, recommendations and solutions were formulated based on the work carried out in collaboration with stakeholders during subsequent workshops. A focus group workshop, attended by policy actors from all Mission Ocean & Waters Lighthouse Areas as well as representatives from the EU and marine innovators, facilitated an in-depth exploration of the study's findings and proposed recommendations. The most prominent solutions and recommendations were distilled based on the input from the focus group resulting in “The Five Commandments”:

1. Allow faster access to testing and licensing, without losing out on the necessary diligence;
2. Improve ways in which local contexts can be included in policy formulation and implementation;
3. Adequate implementation of existing regulations, including foreseeing the necessary resources for this on all levels;
4. Be open and clear about hindering factors that limited development of business and initiatives so that others can learn from it;
5. Redefinition of profit: include the triple bottom approach where economic, social and ecological factors are taken into account.

Acronyms & Abbreviations

Table 1. Table of abbreviations and acronyms used in PREP4BLUE and the document

Acronym / Abbreviation	Signification
CCC	Climate City Contract
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
EC	European Commission
EGCS	Exhaust Gas Cleaning Systems
IA	Innovation Action
IMO	International Maritime Organization
IMT	Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture
LH(s)	Mission Lighthouse(s)
MARPOL	The International Convention for the Prevention of Pollution from Ships
MO	Mission Ocean & Waters / Mission “Restore Our Ocean & Waters by 2030)
MPA	Marine Protected Area
MSFD	Marine Strategy Framework Directive
MSP	Marine Spatial Planning
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
ORE	Offshore Renewable Energy
P4B	PREP4BLUE
R&I	Research & Innovation
RED	Renewable Energy Directive
SECA	Sulphur Emission Control Area
WFD	Water Framework Directive

1 Introduction

The *Mission Ocean and Waters* was launched within the framework of the Horizon Europe Missions. These Missions are tackling some of the biggest challenges (fighting cancer, climate change, protecting our ocean and waters, living in greener cities and ensuring soil health and food) that our world is dealing with. The approach of these Missions tries to initiate interdisciplinary linkages, mobilise the involved stakeholders and leverage investments toward the Mission goals (European Commission, 2021).

The Mission Ocean & Waters (MO), in support of the European Green Deal, aims to restore the health of our ocean, seas and waters by 2030. This general objective will be supported by setting forward three specific goals: 1) protect and restore marine and freshwater ecosystems and biodiversity, 2) prevent and eliminate pollution of our ocean, and 3) make the Blue Economy sustainable, carbon neutral and circular (Lescrauwaet et al., 2022).

In order to successfully implement the Mission Ocean & Waters (MO), two different phases are identified. The first phase (2021 to 2025) will focus on development and piloting. For this, specific Lighthouse areas (LHs) will pilot one specific MO goal, see Figure 1.

Figure 1: Lighthouses for the Mission Ocean and Waters, with their objective for the Mission first phase

This will be followed by a second phase (2025 to 2030) that handles the deployment and upscaling (European Commission, 2021).

During the first phase, important, excellent, impact-driven research and innovation (R&I) actions will be carried out. In particular, new transformative solutions will be piloted and tested for ecosystem restoration, pollution reduction, and developing circular and carbon-neutral blue economy activities (see Figure 2).

Figure 2: Main themes for the first series of Mission Ocean and Waters Innovation Actions (IA)

The PREP4BLUE project was launched to support the development and piloting phase of the MO. The project's overarching objective is to develop the R&I implementation modalities required to achieve the MO Objectives and facilitate a successful first phase.

Within the framework of PREP4BLUE, six objectives were put forward. One of these focuses on the support for creating an enabling environment from a regulatory and economic perspective, enabling private/public investments needed in future MO projects, which is translated into Work Package 5 (WP5).

Within WP5, task 5.2 focuses on the transformational solutions that will be piloted and tested throughout the different Lighthouses and, more specifically, on the policy and regulation context in which they will operate. As illustrated by the conclusions of the UNITED project (Dasgupta et al., 2023), maritime policy and regulation were traditionally developed on a sector-by-sector basis, and the existing regulatory framework may pose some challenges to the deployment of ocean multi-use projects. Reference can also be made to the Blue Economy Report 2022 (European Commission, 2022), where it is stated – when discussing the possibilities for shared use of windfarms – that “For research, this could also mean that there are still many unanswered questions that form the basis for new and appropriate legislations as well as regulations.” For the Offshore Renewable Energy (ORE) sector, Apolonia et al., (2021) state “Firstly, legislation governing ocean energy as a specific sector is rare, both at national and international levels. ORE targets are often unrealistic, and funding schemes are unsuitable, leading to loss of credibility and making investors reluctant to invest in the sector”. With regard to the research and marketing of micro-algae, the complexity of the authorisation procedures for novel foods, the low number of species that can be cultivated, the prohibition on selling certain species (and related products) in markets outside the EU and the difficulties in accessing legislative

information and updates on microalgae are among the crucial problems identified to develop markets (Rumin et al., 2021). Small-scale innovative technologies for water and wastewater treatment can achieve ready-to-use, high-quality recovered/treated water on-site, but the loop cannot be closed in most cases due to legislative barriers (Cipolletta et al., 2021).

By extension, this conclusion may apply to several innovative solutions being developed within the Mission Ocean and Waters. Therefore, the current report will focus on the possible enablers and barriers to the practical and large-scale roll-out of the technologies and solutions currently in the development or pilot phase. It aims to provide an overview of relevant policies and regulations and give attention to challenges experienced by “the boots on the ground” innovators within the Mission Ocean & Waters context. Actionable suggestions for navigating the path forward are given and can form a part of the policy roadmap towards success for current and future LH projects.

The report is built up as follows:

- Chapter 1 constitutes the introductory chapter.
- Chapter 2 gives an overview of the methodology used to develop the analysis presented in this report.
- Chapter 3 delves deeper into the Policy Heatmap analysis.
- Chapter 4 focuses on the identified barriers and enablers in policy and regulation.
- Chapter 5 outlines recommendations and solutions.
- Chapter 6 offers a general conclusion.

2 Methodology

The overall objective of PREP4BLUE Task 5.2 is to draw concrete recommendations linked to policy and regulation to enable the operational application of the innovations developed within the Mission Lighthouses. To this end, several steps were taken.

A top-down approach was used as a first step, mapping possible linked policies. In the following phase, a bottom-up assessment of barriers and enablers was made based on this list and with input from an extensive set of interviews, indicating possible solutions. At the same time, case studies were collected from the different regions. Finally, workshops with various stakeholders (policy actors, innovators, researchers, industry) reflected on these conclusions.

The sections below elaborate on the methods used and the relevant intermediate results (the heatmap).

2.1 Policy heatmap

The objective of the policy heatmap was to establish a theoretical foundation for subsequent work by mapping existing European policies and regulations in relation to Mission Ocean & Waters' overarching objectives. The primary aim of the heatmap is to offer insight into the alignment between European legislation and the thematic focus areas of the four Lighthouses in the construction of the heatmap; the focus was on the relevant EU directives enacted by local governments and EU targets. As stated by Frantzi et al. (2021), top-down EU policies are the most influential legislation relevant to marine litter management, often forming the basis of regional and national plans.

The current iteration of the heatmap, as further described in Chapter 3, was set up focusing on the overarching Mission Objectives and, in addition, several specific innovation themes. The idea and set-up of the map is such that at later stages, when relevant, it can be further expanded with upcoming innovation themes.

2.1.1 Selection of specific Lighthouse themes & listing of EU policy

The main intention was to keep the output of the task as close as possible to practical applicability for current and future Lighthouses. Therefore, the focus was kept on specific LH themes as cases. To this end, based on the work programmes linked to the Mission Ocean & Waters, 24 Lighthouse themes were identified. During a project partner workshop, two themes per region were selected for further detailed uptake in the heatmap study.

To maintain the link to the overarching Mission framework, the heatmap analysis was also carried out for the general Lighthouse Objectives (see Figure 1). In this way, the user first gets a general view of the relationship between policies and the broad Objectives of the Mission, as well as maintaining the option of using this heatmap as a living document: at a later stage, Lighthouse themes can be added to the three main general Objectives.

Further, two specific LH themes were added for each of the three main objectives of Mission Ocean & Waters to have a sufficient geographical and thematic spread.

Currently, the following LH themes are included in the heatmap:

- The Danube & Atlantic/Arctic Region:
 - Main objective: Protect and restore marine and freshwater ecosystems and biodiversity;

- LH specific theme: Increased population of fish/molluscs/etc. in Danube;
- LH specific theme: Innovation to counteract marine biodiversity loss (shipping, fisheries, invasive species, nursery habitats).
- Mediterranean Sea:
 - Main objective: Prevent and eliminate pollution;
 - LH specific theme: Upstream prevention of litter by design/chemical pollutants;
 - LH specific theme: Circular design of fishing gear.
- Baltic and North Sea:
 - Main objective: Carbon neutral and circular blue economy;
 - LH specific theme: Bringing algae-based products to the market: human food, aquaculture feed, waste-water treatment, materials, circular and sustainable textiles, pharma;
 - LH specific theme: Mussel and seaweed aquaculture within Offshore Wind Farms and Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture (IMT).

Based on the above-selected themes, a desktop study was conducted for the listing of relevant policies, starting from Verleye et al. (2018), as well as a general screening of EU publications. This was then further supplemented by the input collected from two surveys: (1) In collaboration with task 5.4 of PREP4BLUE (lead by CPMR), a question on the policy was included in a survey that was sent out to CPMR members, and (2) the expertise within the PREP4BLUE Consortium was consulted through an internal survey.

2.2 In-depth interviews

To comprehensively understand the practical barriers and enablers encountered in the implementation of innovative technologies, particularly those developed within the Mission Ocean & Waters Lighthouses, a series of in-depth interviews were conducted. These interviews addressed various aspects, including the perceived impact and importance of policies and regulations in facilitating project activities, participants' familiarity with the policy framework, and concrete examples and case studies that illustrated implications for practice.

A total of 16 interviews were conducted with policymakers and innovation project leaders from both the research and industry sectors. A detailed list of interview questions can be found in Appendix 8.1.

The information gleaned from these interviews were analysed thoroughly. Based on this analysis, initial trends pertaining to barriers and enablers were identified. These insights subsequently formed the foundation for discussions during two workshops, as detailed in Chapter 2.3. and are further elaborated in Chapter 4.2 (Enablers), 4.3 (Barriers) and 5 (Recommendations and solutions).

Moreover, information from the interviews on relevant local policy was used to enrich the heatmap, providing additional context and depth. It stands to note that from a total of 82 identified policy documents in the heatmap, 15 were mentioned during the interviews. These were previously recognised as relevant to one or more Mission Ocean & Waters (MO) Objectives. The interviewees identified 10 new documents (between communications, directives, regulations, and strategies) not identified by the heatmap to have a direct link to the Mission Objectives. There are policy documents that are not directly related to the Objectives of MO; however, they are still relevant to the development and implementation of projects within this framework.

In addition, selected case studies emerging from the interviews are taken up in the following chapters of this report, further enriching our understanding of the practical implications of policies and regulations for innovation implementation within Mission Ocean & Waters.

2.3 Workshops

The insights gained from the interviews, from which a list of drivers and barriers was distilled, served as the basis for a **first stakeholder workshop**. This workshop took place during the [1st Mission Arena](#) in Gothenburg (November 2023), organised by LH CSA Project BlueMissionBANOS and focused on exploring business models and approaches to strengthen the sustainable blue economy. Participants included representatives from the policy, industry and research sectors.

During the workshop, participants were briefed on the preliminary findings from the interviews and were asked to reflect on a series of questions related to business and innovation. In particular, for this deliverable, participants were asked to reflect on policy measures that could facilitate the operational adoption of useful innovations in support of the sustainable blue economy.

The insights generated by the workshop discussions were analysed in-depth. The results of this analysis were then clustered and incorporated into the recommendations and solutions presented in the following chapters of this report.

A **focus group workshop** was organised in April 2024. This was set up as a focus group and served as a platform to engage policy representatives, both at regional and EU level, in an interactive discussion on the results and findings of our study. An agenda for the workshop can be found in Appendix 1.1.

The workshop, attended by policy actors from all Mission Ocean & Waters Lighthouse Areas as well as representatives from the EU and marine innovators, facilitated an in-depth exploration of the study's findings and proposed recommendations. Additional input for the recommendations, as well as leads to distil the most important solutions and recommendations, were taken from the workshop feedback.

3 Policy Heatmap

Overall, 77 EU-level documents were considered, consisting of 1 recommendation, 28 communications, 31 directives, 15 regulations and two other policy documents (implementation decision and plan). In addition, from the interviews, five examples of local legislation directly linked to the Mission Objectives were brought forward.

EUROPEAN LEGISLATION	NAME	DESCRIPTION	Protect and restore marine and freshwater ecosystems and biodiversity (Danube & Atlantic-Arctic)			Prevent and eliminate pollution of our ocean, seas and waters (Med)			Make sustainable Blue Economy carbon neutral and circular (BANOS)		
			GENERAL OBJECTIVE	Increased population of fish/mollusks/etc. in Danube	Innovation to counteract marine biodiversity loss	GENERAL OBJECTIVE	Upstream prevention of litter/chemical pollutants	Circular design of fishing gear	GENERAL OBJECTIVE	Bringing Algae based products to the market	Mussel and seaweed aquaculture within OWFs and IMT
Recommendation	Recommendation on integrated coastal zone management	2002/413 - Implementation of Integrated Coastal Zone Management in Europe	I.a.								
Communication	Erika I	COM(2000) 142 final - Communication to Parliament and the Council on the safety of the seaborne oil trade (Erika I)				Introduc-tion: Art. 8					
	Erika II	COM (2000) 802: Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament and the Council on a second set of community measures on maritime safety following the sinking of the oil tanker Erika									
	Erika III	COM (2005) 585: Communication from the Commission - Third package of legislative measures on maritime safety in the European Union									

Figure 3: Policy heatmap extract. The full policy heatmap can be found in Appendix 8.4

Starting from the comprehensive list of policy documents, compiled based on the desktop research and the survey results, an analysis of the heatmap was carried out to assess the correlation between each general objective and the chosen Lighthouse themes to determine if a connection exists with the listed policies. To accomplish this, the underlying policy documents associated with each listed legislation were examined. This involved a systematic screening of the policy text for relevant keywords, which served as indicators of alignment with the Objectives. Subsequently, the policy documents were thoroughly reviewed based on the identified keywords to ascertain their relevance to our analysis.

The keywords used for the listed Objectives/themes can be found in Appendix 8.3.

The results are then illustrated by means of a colour scheme (green/red) to indicate if the supporting policy documents of certain legislation mention the general Objectives and/or Lighthouse themes. The result can be found in Appendix 0.

In general, the occurrence was distributed quite evenly across all three overarching themes, with "Prevent and eliminate pollution" and "Protect and restore marine and freshwater ecosystems and biodiversity" appearing in approximately 60% of the documents, while "Make the Blue Economy Carbon Neutral and Circular" featured in slightly over half of them. Notably, the outlier among specific

topics was “*innovation to counteract marine biodiversity loss*”, present in around 40% of cases, while highly specialised topics like the circular design or fishing gear were found in only 10% of the documents, which may be expected given their specificity.

Regarding policy documents, it is evident that some are very specific and therefore mainly focus on one theme, while others are broader and have links to the three general themes. In total, 23% of the documents are linked to each of the three main objectives of Mission Ocean & Waters, and 35% are linked to two of the main Objectives. This indicates that the objectives (and innovations that will be achieved within these objectives) will evolve within a broad framework of existing and linked policies. Individually, with links to all main objectives and more than half of the managed innovation requests, the Biodiversity Strategy 2030, the Farm to Fork Strategy, and the regulation for the European Maritime, Fisheries, and Aquaculture Fund are policy documents that stand out prominently.

4 Enablers and Barriers in Policy and Regulations

The current chapter will focus on the enabling and hindering aspects of policy and regulation linked to the (technological) innovations and processes brought forward in the Mission Ocean & Waters.

The information consolidated in this chapter relies mainly on the insights gained from the interviews and surveys. Additional information from workshops have also been added where relevant. The data from the individual interviews and surveys have been systematically compiled into higher-level concepts so that the findings are presented coherently and clearly. Each aspect covered is accompanied by a brief interpretation that clarifies its meaning within the context of policy and regulation.

Moreover, where possible, examples from the surveys and interviews are cited to underline the practical relevance of the concepts discussed. These examples serve not only to strengthen the link between theory and practice but also to inspire further exploration and application in relevant areas. It can be noted that the conclusions extend beyond topics directly tied to Mission Ocean & Waters, although the Mission served as the overarching framework for all interviews and surveys.

4.1 Information structuring framework

As stated before, the interviews delivered a rich but scattered source of information on various aspects of innovative research themes in relation to policy and regulation. To structure the information in chapters 4 and 5, each of the topics was assigned to one of the stages based on the policy cycle (Figure 4) as described in (Macintosh, 2004). The policy cycle, therefore, has several advantages:

- First, the different phases of the process are clearly described in terms of their objectives;
- Second, it enables a detailed content analysis of the individual phases;
- Third, it offers a new perspective on the impact-oriented design and the implementation of participation projects in all phases (Edelmann & Albrecht, 2023).

Figure 4: Policy Cycle (based on Macintosh, 2004)

The five main stages of the Policy Cycle (Figure 4):

- **Agenda setting & thematic focus:** involves identifying the necessity for policy action and specifying the problem to be tackled, which can stem from shifts in government, environmental changes, evolving developments, or emerging issues.
- **Analysis phase:** During the analysis phase, challenges and opportunities related to an agenda item are clearly defined to draft a policy document, involving gathering evidence from various sources, understanding the political context, developing multiple options, conducting cost-benefit analysis, and advising decision-makers.
- **Policy creation:** Creating the policy involves crafting a viable policy document through mechanisms such as formal consultation, risk analysis, pilot studies, and implementation planning.
- **Policy implementation and adoption:** encompasses drafting legislation, regulations, guidance, and a delivery plan.
- **Monitoring policy:** entails evaluating and reviewing its implementation through research evidence, user perspectives, and horizon scanning.

4.2 Enablers

4.2.1 Policy as a catalyser for investments and innovation (Agenda setting & thematic focus)

Policies promoting and facilitating investments can be powerful tools to attract investment for innovation and maximise its contribution to development. The quality of investment-related policies and the overall investment climate determine the success of the investments (OECD, 2015). The implementation of policies may boost a sector in a certain direction and consequently give more

opportunities for innovators and investors. Certain technological developments can therefore be accelerated when in line with the established policy framework.

- *Exhaust gas cleaning systems*

The EU Directive 2016/802 relating to a reduction in the sulphur content of certain liquid fuels facilitated a regulation-driven demand and gave a boost to the industry to produce exhaust gas cleaning systems (EGCS).

- *Scrubber and Ballast water treatment systems*

In 2004, the International Marine Organisation (IMO) adopted the International Convention for the Control and Management of Ships' Ballast Water and Sediments resulting in the production of scrubber and ballast water treatment systems based on different technologies to comply with the regulations.

- *Valencian 2030 Climate Mission*

The Valencian 2030 Climate Mission aims to achieve climate neutrality by 2030 and addresses several sustainable goals such as expanding green spaces, stimulating green energy, and enhancing public health. With this strategy, Valencia enables local transition and innovation towards climate neutrality. It uses the Climate City Contract (CCC) of the European Mission Cities to interlink commitments, actions and (private) investments.

4.2.2 Supporting cooperation (Agenda setting & thematic focus)

Due to the transboundary nature of the marine environment, cooperation and coordination across neighbouring countries is essential. This allows us to tackle anthropogenic pressures on the environment and effectively manage and protect marine resources while avoiding user conflicts (van Tatenhove et al., 2014). EU policies and regulations act as enablers for cooperation and coordination amongst Member States. Directives such as the MSP¹ set an obligation to cooperate at sea level basin, with Member and non-Member States, to achieve efficient management and conservation of marine resources (Friess & Grémaud-Colombier, 2021). Moreover, the EU regulatory framework allows for the development of information-sharing platforms, resource allocation and standardisation, market incentives, and technology pushes – including funding for research and development through Horizon Europe and Horizon 2020 programmes – as well as setting common targets and strategies (Apolonia et al., 2021). EU Directives also allow for the development of expert groups and discussion platforms, fuelling information sharing and exchange of experiences, such as for example the technical working groups under the MSFD.

¹ Directive 2014/89/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 July 2014 establishing a framework for maritime spatial planning

- *Joint Declaration on the Protection of the Wadden Sea*

Some marine Natura 2000 sites run across national borders and as such, are managed by several countries. The Wadden Sea, located in the southern North Sea has been designated as both a Natura 2000 site, a UNESCO World Heritage Site and a RAMSAR site due to the important presence of intertidal sands and mud flats. Its management is a great example of transboundary cooperation. Indeed, the three neighbouring countries (Denmark, Germany and The Netherlands) agreed to jointly manage the site through the Trilateral Wadden Sea Cooperation. The case study is considered highly relevant for cross-border management of transitional waters (Povilanskas, 2013).

- *The Regional Strategy of Southwest Finland 2040*

The Regional Strategy of Southwest Finland, adopted in 2022 is a key guiding document that pushes towards the Mission Ocean & Waters Objectives. The strategy was developed in extensive cooperation with various actors, through a yearlong participatory process involving about 300 regional experts. The implementation and monitoring are also to be carried out through regional partnerships.

4.2.3 Implementation of new technologies (Agenda setting and thematic focus)

The enactment of legislations can push marine sectors in a certain direction forcing these sectors to innovate and implement new technologies. With the implementation of different EU directives such as the Water Framework Directive (WFD) (2000/60/EC), Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) (2008/56/EC), Species and Habitats Directive (92/43/EEC), and Birds Directive (79/409/EEC), marine sectors are required to take greater consideration of potential environmental impacts of their activities. The study of Pelkmans & Renda (2014) showed that more prescriptive regulation tends to hamper innovation, whereas more flexible regulation stimulates innovative developments. Objective-driven and market-oriented regulation appear to be favourable to stimulate innovative responses by enterprises (Pelkmans & Renda, 2014).

- *The Italian Salvamare Law*

The "Salvamare Law" (Law No. 60/2022 "Provisions for the recovery of waste at sea and in inland waters and for the promotion of the circular economy"), which came into force following the transposition of Directive 2019/883/EU, aims to contribute to the recovery of the marine, lake and river ecosystem as well as to promote the circular economy, by encouraging the recovery of accidentally fished waste and voluntarily collected waste. In addition, with a view to environmental sustainability, it aims to encourage voluntary campaigns to clean up the sea and raise public awareness for the dissemination of virtuous behavioural models aimed at preventing the abandonment of waste in marine-coastal environments. The Salvamare Law enables the introduction of waste collection in fishing ports of waste accidentally caught in the nets of fishing boats, preventing it from being thrown back into the sea because they are no longer considered special waste and therefore overtaxed.

- *Danish Mussel Policy*

In Denmark, the Danish Mussel Policy was implemented in 2014 to enable an ecosystem-based approach to the management of bivalve fisheries in Natura2000 areas. Several management strategies were put in place to meet the objectives of the Danish Mussel Policy (Nielsen et al., 2021).

This resulted, for example, in the development of high-resolution electronic monitoring systems to track fishing activities (Dalskov et al., 2021).

- *Sulphur Emission Control Area (SECA)*

The International Maritime Organization (IMO) has designated the North Sea and the Baltic Sea as Sulphur Emission Control Areas (SECAs). Within these regions, ships are required to use fuel with a maximum sulphur content of 0.1%; as such, this regulation aims to reduce sulphur emissions from marine traffic, thereby improving air quality in ports and territorial waters. As stated in Stalmokaitė & Yliskylä-Peuralahti (2019): Arguably, SECA’s regulatory requirement was an important regime-level catalyst that created incentives for companies to revise their strategies and opened a window of opportunity for different moves among incumbent shipping companies. Three interviewed shipping companies chose to invest in more radical or transitional environmental innovations, specifically LNG and methanol-driven vessels.

4.2.4 Supporting nature restoration and conservation (Agenda setting and thematic focus)

Only 15% of European habitats are currently considered in good conditions, with coastal habitats particularly affected by human activities (European Environment Agency, 2019). From the interviews, the explicit integration of goals into policy and regulation is seen as a powerful tool for nature restoration and conservation and, as such, as a support for the solutions developed within the Mission Ocean & Waters. A remark that could be made here is the attention to language gaps between different stakeholders in the policy process: as it was pointed out in the interviews, there is a gap between how policymakers and scientists understand concepts, e.g., on the difference between restoration and conservation. In one of the interviews, the example was given of the positive effects on biodiversity in offshore windfarm areas, which in certain cases, although beneficial, are not always conservation efforts and, as such, cannot be equalled to Marine Protected Areas (or count towards the 30 by 30 goal as stated in the EU Biodiversity Strategy²).

The Communication on the Sustainable Blue Economy (COM(2021)240) states that “Biodiversity conservation and restoration also present economic opportunities”. A great example of legislation explicitly geared towards nature restoration is the EU Restoration Law, adopted by the EU Parliament in early 2024, under the Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, which sets a target of at least 30% of marine and terrestrial habitats restored by 2030, 60% by 2040 and 90% by 2050, prioritising Natura 2000 areas. The enforcement of the EU Restoration Law will impose the development and adoption of national restoration plans by Member States to achieve the objectives. It is to be noted however, that other legal instruments also offer opportunities to serve as a framework for restoration, which may have been underused: during interviews, examples were given of the Floods Directive, but also the Environmental Liability directive (Annex II).

² COMMUNICATION FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT, THE COUNCIL, THE EUROPEAN ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL COMMITTEE AND THE COMMITTEE OF THE REGIONS EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 Bringing nature back into our lives COM/2020/380 final

4.2.5 Directionality (Policy implementation and adoption)

Existing regulation and strategies outline a common direction and ambition regarding the goals of thematic objectives (e.g. biodiversity, pollution and blue economy and decarbonisation). European Missions, for example, aim to encourage innovation around certain challenges (conquering cancer, restoring oceans and making cities climate-neutral). This approach can be defined as promoting innovations that contribute to a particular direction of transformative change (Parks, 2022; Weber & Rohrer, 2012). Policies and regulations are considered important drivers to move things forward in a common direction, but this does not necessarily mean that a variety of pathways can't be explored (Parks, 2022).

- *EU Green Deal*

The European Green Deal, launched in 2019, aims to achieve climate neutrality in Europe by 2050. It targets firstly a reduction of 55% of greenhouse gases by 2030. As a general policy strategy, the Green Deal outlines ambitions and goals in different policy sectors (Fetting, 2020).

- *Bremen Hydrogen Strategy*

In Germany, the Northern German Hydrogen Strategy was launched in 2019 to optimize the use of the onshore and offshore power generation capacities, cavern gas storage facilities and seaports in the region, and to establish a green hydrogen economy by 2035. To concretize this approach, Bremen has developed the Bremen Hydrogen Strategy, in which both actual projects and actions, as well as supporting measures (such as the establishment of a Hydrogen Support Office) are included. The responsibility for implementing Bremen's hydrogen strategy lies in the hands of the senate departments according to the senate's distribution of business (Bremen Hydrogen Strategy, 2021).

4.2.6 Promoting Common Standards (Policy implementation and adoption)

EU Directives relevant to the management and conservation of the marine environment, such as the Birds and Nature Directives, the Marine Spatial Planning (MSP) Directive, and the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD), set up common standards across the Member States, which facilitates the development of regional ocean initiatives and solutions. The push of the EU towards marine spatial planning, through firstly the 2008 *"Roadmap for Maritime Spatial Planning: Achieving Common Principles in the EU"* and then, through the 2014 MSP Directive, to set up common principles across Europe, focusing on cross-border aspects and establishing a common framework (Friess & Grémaud-Colombier, 2021). Common standards, like MSP and Integrated Maritime Policy (IMP), guide public authorities and stakeholders to coordinate their actions and, in this case, optimise the use of marine space to benefit economic development and the marine environment (COM/2008/0791).

In the framework of the MSP and MSFD Directives, France and Spain undertook in 2018 a joint study of marine mammals and seabirds in the Gulf of Lion, as these species are protected in both countries' MPAs. This has been a crucial first step towards assessments of transboundary issues and coherent planning and management of marine environments. This example of successful cross-border cooperation paves the way for effective marine spatial planning in the Mediterranean (Chloé et al., 2019).

4.2.7 Green taxonomy (Policy implementation and adoption)

As stated under 4.2.2, policies can be a powerful tool to attract and facilitate investments and maximise innovative developments. In addition, the sustainability of these investments is of high importance as part of the EU's Sustainable Finance Framework. In the Action Plan on Financing Sustainable Growth adopted by the EC in 2018, the Commission committed to establishing a general classification system for sustainable economic activities, which led to the Taxonomy Regulation³. The EU Taxonomy is a cornerstone in the EU's Sustainable Finance Framework and an important market transparency tool to ensure a transition aligned with the EU Green Deal objectives. The Taxonomy Regulation sets out the four overarching conditions an economic activity must meet to qualify as environmentally sustainable and does so for six ecological objectives, including the sustainable use and protection of water and marine resources (Martens et al., 2023; OECD, 2020).

- *Renewable Energy Directive III (RED III)*

The EU Directive 2023/2413 amending the EU Directive 2018/2001 on the promotion of the use of energy from renewable sources (recast) is an important instrument for industrial players as it gives them legal certainty. By virtue of this framework, industrial players invest in sustainable developments and contribute to the green transition of the economy as targeted by the EU Green Deal.

- *Remarks from stakeholders on Green Taxonomy*

Based on the insights collected during the first workshop, a general belief in the EU Taxonomy Regulation was noted. Participants agreed that green taxonomy can be a very successful tool. However, some concerns remained on the benefits for small companies and companies with a business model targeting sustainable gains rather than financial benefits. In addition, participants notified that the implementation of the Taxonomy Regulation will have an influence on the labelling of products and the transparency of companies.

4.3 Barriers

4.3.1 Ambiguity of definitions (Policy creation)

Definitions set up in the different relevant EU Directives often lack clarity, which leads to challenges in terms of the application and implementation of regulations. Several EU Directives treat specific issues within specific sectors, using a wide range of terminology without clearly defining the exact concept, aim and framework, leaving space for ambiguity and potentially not reaching the target. As cited by one interviewee: *"They shouldn't impose really strict ways of doing things, because otherwise it won't be flexible enough to be implemented in a different context. But they should clearly define what is what and what are the outputs expected"*.

- *Marine Spatial Planning*

Within the MSP Directive, the requirements are loosely formulated and ambiguous, while it is emphasised that the competency for designing and implementing the plans is resting with the

³ Regulation (EU) 2020/852 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 18 June 2020 on the establishment of a framework to facilitate sustainable investment, and amending Regulation (EU) 2019/2088

Member States (Kirkfeldt et al., 2020). Hence, this may ensure non-uniform implementation among Member States.

- *Marine Strategy Framework Directive*

The wording in the MSFD is vague on certain points, and the Good Environmental Status (GES) is only given a general definition with specificities to be defined by each Member State (Puharinen, 2023). Formulation of requirements and objectives are open for interpretation, which can generate misunderstandings and conflicts (Kirkfeldt et al., 2020). As such, there is a need for clear guidance for sustainability concepts used in EU Directives relevant to the marine environment. Addressing this lack of clarity would ensure effective implementation of EU Directives (Puharinen, 2023).

- *Single Use Plastics Directive*

With the Directive (EU) 2019/904, the EU aims to reduce the impact of certain plastic products on the environment. However, there are several shortcomings in terms of labelling and definitions within the directive, resulting in a difference between the intended and actual outcome. The policy ended up missing the target by not stopping the use of plastics but rather changing the material types.

4.3.2 Disparity of implementation (Policy implementation and adoption)

EU Member States display important disparities in terms of implementation of EU directives (Lampinen & Uusikylä, 1998). Indeed, while the EU gives direction by adopting directives and decisions, the responsibility of effectively implementing them is left to the Member States. Directives need to be transposed into national laws, either through new domestic legislation or through amendments to existing ones. For example, the Birds and Habitats Directive has been successfully transposed into national laws. This requires intense cooperation and coordination amongst authorities at national, regional and local levels, as well as with those of neighbouring countries. Lack of capacity can hinder the effective implementation at national level. Moreover, when directives are transposed at national level there can be confusion as to which institutions are responsible for carrying out the implementation and monitoring (Lampinen & Uusikylä, 1998). Adopting innovations designed at the EU level can face challenges due to stricter regulations in certain countries (Lampinen & Uusikylä, 1998). Even where governance is concentrated rather than dispersed, implementation will still be highly dependent on the local context (Hudson et al., 2019). A study on the legal and regulatory framework for Marine Sustainability Policy Calado et al. (2023) noted that “Results suggested that the difference in implementation of relevant marine policy in the North Atlantic countries stem from the different national approaches to marine policy. For instance, France and the UK have a more bottom-up approach, while other countries, such as Portugal, exhibit a more top-down approach to marine policy and governance” (Calado et al., 2018; Pinto et al., 2015). One interviewee also stated that countries could have different stages of development and/or interest and that, therefore, cookie-cutter approaches to pushing forward new developments/technologies (e.g. on aquaculture) will not always work.

- *Marine Spatial Planning*

The implementation of the EU Directive (2014/89/EU) into national laws is still lacking in several EU Member States. Marine Spatial Planning aims at an efficient, safe and sustainable management of

the use of our seas and oceans, but by bringing all activities and sectors around the table it also complicates the implementation at different levels and dimensions.

- *Port Reception Facilities*

To protect the marine environment against the negative effects from discharges of waste from ships using ports in the EU, the European Commission has adopted the EU Directive (2019/883/EU) on port reception facilities, in line with the International Convention for the Prevention of Pollution from Ships (MARPOL). This requires ports to provide adequate facilities to collect all sorts of waste from ships. However, while MARPOL provides a comprehensive framework, it does not provide effective enforcement mechanisms. Furthermore, the directive is interpreted differently by Member States leading to additional confusion among ports and other stakeholders, and hence disparity of implementation at a national level.

- *Unmanned aircraft – drones*

There are currently disparities between the EU Directive (2019/947/EU) and national legislation on flying drones, which makes it difficult to fully explore the potential of the innovative technologies. Besides, national legislations on flying drones also hampered the application of new technologies in certain coastal and marine areas (e.g. permits to fly over ports). In addition, these inconveniences are also reflected in additional difficulties when it comes to insurance.

- *Transversal remark*

During the interviews it was quoted that the amount of legislation coming from EU towards national level is a challenge and especially difficult for small countries with limited capacity to absorb and implement them all within sometimes unrealistic timelines.

4.3.3 Contradictions and prioritisation in existing policies (Policy implementation and adoption)

Several EU Directives have been adopted, displaying a variety of targets and objectives for Member States to reach. However, these can sometimes lead to conflict. Think of challenges in the development of innovations with the composition of new materials that might fall under the scope of existing regulations or that cause disturbances, such as new drones for cleaning the seafloor, but that cause underwater noise. This is particularly the case within the legal framework revolving around the marine environment, where directives aiming at protecting biodiversity might overlap with those pushing for the development of the blue economy. Governance systems for fisheries, power generation, irrigation, aquaculture, marine biodiversity conservation, and other coastal and maritime activities are typically organised to manage conflicts within sectors rather than across them (Bellanger et al., 2020). For example, the development of marine renewable energies requires important new allocations of marine spaces, which can conflict with established marine protected areas (Christie et al., 2014; Vaughan & Agardy, 2020). It is then difficult to know which sector has priority, leading to insecurity.

- *In Slovenia, there have been notable initiatives aimed at replacing traditional plastic cups with bioplastic alternatives. However, challenges arise due to existing regulations governing the use of plastic cups, which are often impractical to meet when transitioning to bioplastic cups. For instance, certain regulations, possibly pertaining to hygiene or cleaning standards, impose strict*

requirements that are difficult to comply with using bioplastic materials, particularly regarding temperature thresholds. Consequently, while the adoption of bioplastic cups may not significantly affect their actual usage, the stringent regulatory framework designed for traditional plastic cups poses obstacles to their implementation.

- *On the Danube, there has at times been the convergence of various directives and projects concerning river management. For example, alongside the flood directive's requirements for river infrastructure, additional initiatives are being developed within the framework of the Water Framework Directive (WFD) to establish a fish pass upstream. Moreover, the Renewable Energy Directive (RED) aims to harness hydropower to maximize electricity generation from the river, showcasing a commitment to sustainable energy solutions. Although integrating these efforts may pose challenges, it also signifies a collective commitment to enhancing the river's ecological and energy potential. The occasionally conflicting demands from these various policy documents can lead to uncertainty regarding the focus of what needs to be achieved.*

4.3.4 Administrative overload (Policy implementation and adoption)

Regulations and policies are indispensable frameworks for innovation, but following up and fulfilling these regulations can also entail administrative obligations. Complying with legal standards requires meticulous documentation, from licence applications to product test reports, entailing a considerable administrative overhead. For scientists and inventors, this paperwork can divert precious time and resources from research and development. Moreover, the complex and evolving nature of regulations requires constant monitoring and updating, which makes paperwork even worse. This can be at the level of countries, implementing new EU regulations, but also small-scale innovators and start-ups in particular may face disproportionate challenges in dealing with these bureaucratic hurdles, potentially hampering their ability to bring new ideas to market. In addition, the amount of legislation coming from the EU towards the national level is a challenge, especially difficult for those small countries with limited capacity to absorb and implement all in the timelines provided.

4.3.5 Inadequacy of certain policies (Policy implementation and adoption)

Policy and regulation are not fit for all and are often put forward to provide a framework for a central issue, but they are not always concerned with and address related aspects. Therefore, policies may lack relevance and applicability in certain cases. Moreover, the impact of regulatory frameworks on applications is complex, making it hard to understand the different challenges and policy needs for all sectors.

- *Animal Welfare Directive*

The EU Directive (2010/63/EU) on the protection of animals used for scientific purposes as amended by Regulation (EU) 2019/1010, considers the same protocol for all organisms. As a result, the same procedures should be followed to perform experiments on rats as on fish larvae, making it very time-demanding (i.e. paperwork, human resources) to use (higher numbers of) non-mammal species. The current directive is clearly designed for experiments with lab animals (e.g. rats) and should be adjusted to ease research with lower animals.

- *Carbon offsetting in marine environments*

Products like seagrass, austere and marina, for instance, possess the remarkable ability to sequester substantial amounts of carbon. However, their potential to offset carbon emissions remains largely unrecognized as a formal means for carbon offsetting. As stated in Dauwe et al. (2023), the blue carbon market does not (yet) fall under existing government regulation, but offsets are bought and sold on the voluntary carbon market. Blue carbon markets are also relatively new compared to their terrestrial counterparts (e.g. reforestation projects in the Amazon) but revenues are projected to grow exponentially in the coming years (some estimate its total projected value to be worth over 50 billion USD by 2030 (Task Force on the Voluntary Carbon Market, 2021).

4.3.6 Lack of communication (Policy implementation and adoption)

Public communication is crucial to support the design and delivery of policies and services (OECD, 2021). In the words of one of the interviewees, it is “balancing good policy with good communication”. Communication plays a crucial role at every stage of the policy cycle (OECD, 2023). Starting with the agenda setting, where transparent dialogue ensures that emerging issues can be identified and feedback from the necessary experts included. During analysis, communication facilitates the exchange of ideas and data so that stakeholders can define challenges and opportunities together to also arrive at a "shared problem". Clear communication channels help convert insights from analysis into actionable strategies and objectives during policy formulation.

Continuous communication ensures stakeholder alignment and timely problem resolution during policy implementation and administration. When monitoring policies, communication enables stakeholders to track progress. However, a lack of communication in either of these stadia can be a major barrier to innovation.

Without effective communication, stakeholders may misunderstand objectives, leading to misaligned priorities and ineffective solutions. Moreover, insufficient dialogue can hamper cooperation and prevent the exchange of different perspectives and innovative ideas. Moreover, poor communication can make stakeholders feel disengaged or excluded from the decision-making process.

When developing the offshore energy grid in Ireland, the community involvement was active from the start. Rather than developing a solution, that is then presented to the community, the community is involved in every step of the process, a process that was inspired by previous iterations on land. Specific community benefit funds have been set up, and a percentage of the revenue from the renewables is made available through these funds. The expertise required in community engagement, akin to that in engineering is acknowledged, and this entails assembling a transdisciplinary team comprising individuals from diverse fields. These team members are now recognised as integral components of the infrastructure team, highlighting the significance of their involvement.

4.3.7 Weak political buy-in (Policy implementation and adoption)

Policymaking is a time-consuming process subject to the political buy-in and agenda of decision-makers. The extent of committed support among policymakers for a particular policy issue is crucial to driving change and innovation and can often be lower than stakeholders seek. However, support from policymakers is required to create regulatory frameworks and facilitate the implementation of

solutions. Furthermore, during the workshop, stakeholder pointed out that a lack of proactivity is observed at all levels of policymaking.

4.3.8 Policy evaluation and actualisation (Policy monitoring)

Policies are conceived, discussed and influenced in a context that is relevant over time and geographical scope. However, as conditions change due to both endogenous and exogenous factors, the relevance of a policy may diminish. This necessitates an adjustment or update to align the policy with current realities so that it remains effective. Changes in societal norms, technological advances, economic shifts and environmental factors are some of the factors that can make a policy need to be adjusted or updated. The risk, as stated during one of the interviews, is that *“you end up protecting something because it’s protected by law and not because of scientific or societal need”*.

A policy without updates risks not accurately reflecting the prevailing conditions for which it was designed, making it less effective in achieving the desired results. This discrepancy between policy objectives and the changing landscape can lead to inefficiencies, inconsistencies and even unintended consequences. Consequently, recognising the need to update policies becomes essential to maintain relevance, effectiveness and responsiveness to emerging challenges and opportunities. In terms of EU policy, regular evaluations and fitness checks are planned. The evaluation findings help the Commission decide whether EU actions should be continued or changed. A fitness check is a type of evaluation that assesses several related actions. It focuses on identifying how different laws, policies, and programmes interact, any inconsistencies or synergies, and their collective impact (European Commission, n.d.).

- *Habitat Directive*

Currently, the EU Habitats Directive of 1992 lists types of habitats, animals and plant species requiring protection in Annexes I and II, with some defined as ‘priority’ habitats or species through protected areas. However, according to Amos (2021), these lists have not been modified since the adoption of the Directive, and as some species and habitats distribution and abundance are prone to change over time, several changes would need to be made to ensure adequate protection. Indeed, some species and habitats not listed as endangered in 1992 are now unprotected by law, while others deemed in need of protection might be in a better state of conservation. However, the European Commission ensures regular evaluations of EU Policy and has published a fitness check of the EU Nature Legislation (European Commission, 2016).

4.4 Policy-specific reflections

During the interviews and workshops, reflections were also made on specific policies. Below is a general overview of the opinions and concerns that were voiced and, as such, give a general appreciation of the perception of the policies.

- Green Deal⁴. Positive aspects that emerge from the interviews are the ambitious goals, as the fact that targets that promote biodiversity, decarbonisation and promotion of renewable energies are included, as well as the fact that a legal framework is in place so investments can be taken. The Green Deal and the Fit for 55 packages are important drivers and important instruments to move things forward at European level. This can be linked to the enabler “Policy as a Catalyser for Investments” (4.2.1) and Supporting Nature Restoration and Conservation (4.2.4). Attention is raised to the fact that the definitions are not always clear, and as such, ambiguity of definitions (4.3.1) can occur. Habitat Directive⁵: The Habitat Directive brings forth positive aspects, such as facilitating the management of Natura 2000 sites across national boundaries and enforcing restoration efforts (4.2.4). However, there are also points of attention to consider. For instance, the habitats listed may prioritise their significance at the EU level rather than acknowledging the importance of ecosystems at the national level (4.3.2). Additionally, while designations remain static, habitats hosting various species may shift due to climate change (4.3.8). Furthermore, if legislation aims to protect specific areas, they are safeguarded by law rather than by scientific or societal necessity.
- MSFD⁶: Positively, the MSFD establishes crucial levels and limits for pollutants alongside thresholds, opening avenues for enhanced monitoring and research (4.2.3). Additionally, it sets common standards, facilitating collaborative efforts such as those seen in the Gulf of Lyon, thus bolstering monitoring standards across regions (4.2.6). However, challenges persist as overlaps with the Water Framework Directive (WFD) complicate land-sea interactions, often leading to disjointed management efforts (4.3.3). Despite its potential to drive the adoption of monitoring technologies, the MSFD also presents hurdles, such as the potential negative impact of new technologies for plastic litter collection, which could produce underwater noise and face constraints under the directive (4.3.3).
- MSP⁷: From the interviews, MSP emerges as a pivotal tool with both positive and negative dimensions in its application. On the positive front, MSP serves as a unifying framework, bringing together various stakeholders (4.2.2). Moreover, it offers legal protection for the sea, establishing strict conditions for activities, thereby underpinning environmental preservation and offering legal security. MSP also supports multi-use projects, facilitating the opening of concessions for new activities and mitigating conflicts among sea users (4.2.1). However, challenges persist as multi-use remains merely mentioned and not effectively enforced, leading to discrepancies in implementation levels (4.3.2). Despite its positive intentions, MSP could have a more substantial impact if multi-use were mandated and enforcement mechanisms strengthened, ensuring its potential for sustainable marine resource management is fully realised (4.3.5).

⁴ COM (2019) 640: Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the European Council, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions - The European Green Deal

⁵ COUNCIL DIRECTIVE 92/43/EEC - on the conservation of natural habitats and of wild fauna and flora

⁶ Directive 2008/56/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 June 2008 establishing a framework for community action in the field of marine environmental policy (Marine Strategy Framework Directive)

⁷ Directive 2014/89/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 July 2014 establishing a framework for maritime spatial planning

- Single Use Plastic Directive⁸: While it addresses the promotion of reusable alternatives, such as cups at festivals, significant gaps persist, particularly concerning labelling and definitions (4.3.5). These deficiencies have led to shifts in targets without effectively curbing the use of problematic materials themselves. Moreover, unclear definitions pose obstacles to the adoption of innovative biopolymer developments (4.3.1). Despite its intent, the directive falls short in addressing crucial issues such as the treatment of old fishing gear upon their return to land. Additionally, vague references to the design of fishing gear underscore the need for coordinated efforts between Member States and industry stakeholders to align with circular economy principles.
- Renewable Energy Directive⁹: Positively, it has ushered in innovative approaches unlocking new potential for renewable energy sources (4.2.3), offering industrial players legal certainty, particularly evident in initiatives like the RED's provisions for hydrogen. However, amidst its strides, there remains a significant area of concern regarding the balance between addressing climate change and preserving ecological integrity. There appears to be an absence of multisectoral collaboration among policymakers from diverse domains, as highlighted by inequalities with the Water Framework Directive (WFD) (4.3.3).
- Marine Protected Areas: A better policy framework for Marine Protected Areas is required. There is currently no strategy to design MPAs, no provision to designate MPAs and no connectivity or network across borders.

⁸ Directive 2019/904/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 June 2019 on the reduction of the impact of certain plastic products on the environment

⁹ Directive 2009/28/EC on the promotion of the use of energy from renewable sources

5 Recommendations and solutions

The subsequent paragraph presents the recommendations and solutions derived from the gathered data. The primary source of information is the workshops, supplemented with relevant insights from surveys and interviews where applicable. Consistent with the methodology employed in the preceding chapter, the same structuring approach, namely the policy cycle, has been adopted. This methodology facilitates the alignment between identified enablers and barriers and the proposed recommendations and solutions.

5.1 General recommendations and solutions

5.1.1 Allow faster access to testing and licensing (Agenda setting and thematic focus)

Start-ups and small companies were reported to experience problems operationalising their business models because of the time-consuming and expensive process of getting licenses and testing opportunities. For small-scale aquaculture farms, for example, a private coastal area where little administration is required for small-scale pilots would be a promising solution (*i.e.* Finnish private coastal areas). For companies and research groups conducting animal experiments with non-mammalian species in the context of certain (policy-oriented) research, exceptions to the licensing process could be made to make it less time-demanding (*i.e.* paperwork, human resources). However, attention should be paid to the balance between favourable conditions for start-ups and possible scale-ups. Allowing faster access to testing and licensing should never be at the expense of the necessary diligence of start-ups. It was discussed that it must be prevented that test zones are that appealing for companies or organisations that they cannot or do not want to leave this zone in function of a possible scale-up. In addition, it was proposed that this enabler should be unified across Member States and existing EU facilities without current purpose (*e.g.* old port areas) could be reoriented in view of this solution.

5.1.2 Favour (long-term) innovation through adjusted cost and tax systems (Agenda setting and thematic focus)

To favour bottom-up innovation, tax systems should be adapted for small producers. Fixed price costs are in general beneficial for large companies and can hinder small enterprises to take the necessary steps in a growth process. Long-term strategies and investments for small companies with a business plan that is not solely based on financial benefits (*e.g.* aquaculture producers with an environmentally friendly approach) should be developed, see also 5.1.3. A strong link between regulations, taxation, subsidies and support was therefore deemed imperative, and frameworks should consider non-linear growth processes of start-ups.

5.1.3 Redefinition of profit (Agenda setting and thematic focus)

In general, profit is considered as the economic benefits and financial contributions of an activity. However, for several companies the social and ecological benefits have a great share in their business models. The triple bottom line approach (people, planet, profit) was put forward by several workshop participants as the targeted (accounting) framework for sustainable development of businesses. This approach incorporates three dimensions of performance: social, environmental and financial, and favours long-term innovation.

5.1.4 Improve ways in which local contexts can be included (Agenda Setting and thematic focus)

Local focus points do not always seem to be reflected in EU legislations. Therefore, it was stated that there is a need for improved ways to include local contexts. Workshop participants pointed out that the local context is certainly a vital part of policymaking in the framework of spatial planning in particular and should always be considered as valuable as other levels (e.g. national, regional, European), as it is an inherent part of these broader contexts. Here, it is important to adjust to the competences of the different levels. For example, the protection of species relevant at national level are not possible if these lack EU relevance. Species or areas require protection in context to their relevance at national level. Certain habitats, e.g. Maerl beds, are not recognised by the Habitats Directive and as a result do not get protection or a Natura2000 status. Therefore, the strong pressure of anchorage from recreational boats still takes place in these Maerl beds.

5.1.5 Carefulness in writing new policy (Policy creation)

Interviewees pointed out that the existing regulations within their field of expertise are enough, but some are underused. Accordingly, the real challenge lies in the implementation of the existing regulation rather than creating new policies to cover new trends. It was suggested that the inclusion of advice from expert groups in legislation drafting can foster a better implementation of the existing regulations. In addition, a careful vetting process led by policy experts is suggested to avoid policy duplication, whereby attention needs to be paid to the impartiality of those experts. A good example of this is the MPA network process in Ireland, where an advisory group was established by the Ministry of Housing, Planning and Local Government (Marine Protected Area Advisory Group, 2020). Nevertheless, several experts also pointed out that a certain nuance is in place here because new legislation is still needed in a few cases. Furthermore, when creating new policy, it needs to be ascertained that enough resources are allocated for the implementation of what is in the policy.

5.1.6 Easier language to understand initiatives, policies, etc. as well as clear definitions (Policy creation)

To ensure an adequate policy implementation and adoption, policy language should be adapted to the audience. During the policy creation process, definitions, restrictions and objectives should be clearly stated in easy understandable language. There should be a clear outline of the expected outputs or results from the frameworks, as well as the expected timelines. In addition, the gaps between policy and science language should be closed to favour unambiguous and progressive policymaking. Furthermore, communication between sectors should be facilitated and awareness (of the timeline of the policy, of the effect of doing nothing, etc.) should be created amongst sectors.

5.1.7 Adequate implementation of existing regulations (Policy implementation and adoption)

As mentioned in paragraph 4.3.2, several existing EU regulations lack proper implementation at national levels. Directives such as the Birds and Habitats, the MSFD, MSP and Environmental Liability Directive are perceived to be underused to restore and protect marine ecosystems. To ensure an adequate implementation of regulations, an in-depth analysis of existing regulations supported by a group of policy experts was suggested (see also recommendation 5.1.5).

5.1.8 Communicate the hindering factors that limited development of business and initiatives (Policy implementation and adoption)

Working towards a positive outcome is the narrative of every policy, project, business or activity, but is commonly not the only outcome. Negative results or hindering factors during a process often stay under-the-radar as it might not be the best promotional material. However, the hindering aspects that limited development are a very valuable outcome for the broader development of a sector. Communicating the negative outcomes of your activities could therefore be incentivised to stimulate efficient business development and accelerate innovation. For example, EU funded projects could be forced to communicate their unsuccessful results through the reporting process, while start-ups can be encouraged to communicate their negative results on a voluntary basis. However, attention should still be drawn here to intellectual property rights. If certain projects or start-ups have to share their unsuccessful ideas, others may gain a market advantage.

5.2 The Five Commandments

Figure 5: "The Five Commandments", a visual representation of the most prominent solutions and recommendations.

6 Conclusions

As a conclusion, this report has provided insights into the multifaceted landscape surrounding the implementation of innovative solutions within Mission Ocean & Waters. The breadth of possible solutions, and the depth of their ramifications in policy and regulation, mean that the challenges and opportunities presented by enablers and barriers are substantial.

Through the synthesis of a top-down policy analysis and a bottom-up stakeholder engagement, key barriers and enablers were identified which must be addressed to facilitate the successful rollout of Mission Ocean & Waters initiatives. Practical examples and regional regulations have been used to illustrate these points, offering inspiration for future endeavours.

Furthermore, the collaborative workshops held throughout this process have sought to bring together diverse groups of stakeholders, fostering dialogue and hopefully igniting inspiration. The recommendations and solutions proposed contain principles that can serve as guidance for future actions, acting as a roadmap for navigating the complex terrain of Mission Ocean & Waters implementation.

Finally, the five commandments serve as a high-level summary of the key messages distilled from the summaries. The graphical layout facilitates their easy dissemination

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8 Appendix

8.1 Interview questions and overview interviewees

8.1.1 Interview questions

- Are there any activities/initiatives or projects in your institute/company/region (cfr. supra) where the legislative or regulatory framework played an important role (positively or negatively)? Can you give one or more examples?
- How familiar are you with the regulatory framework for these activities/initiatives or projects? Besides these activities/initiatives or projects, are you further engaged in policy and regulation?
- Focusing on this initiative/activity: do you consider the regional/local or European level regulation and policy having the most influence?
- And in this case, does the regulation and policy have this positive or negative influence on the activity?
 - Which policies or regulations are hindering this activity?
 - How are these hindering your work in this activity and how do you deal with this?
 - How would you suggest solving this problem?
 - Regarding this hurdle, was the regulatory framework the only aspect creating an obstacle or were there other factors playing a role as well?
 - To what extent would you consider the regulations being a barrier? Was it the main obstacle or rather a smaller issue in the bigger picture?
 - Which policies or regulations are supporting this activity?
 - How do these support your work and how do you make use of it?
 - Is this support sufficient or is there any improvement possible?
 - Are any of these regulations linked to an EU policy or regulation?
- With the previous questions in mind, are there any additional specific activities/ projects/ initiatives that you see as a possible case study to discuss? Did you experience specific cases (upscaling or implementation of e.g. aquaculture, offshore wind / innovation in equipment, fishing gear, etc. / measures against pollution / etc.) where key obstacles or enablers were in place for your specific innovation needs?
 - Which actors? Which region? How long has this been going on?

8.1.2 Overview interviewees

The following graphs give a graphical overview of the interviewees, the sectors they represent, their gender distribution, as well as the distribution over the lighthouse areas as in the triple helix.

Distribution over LH Areas

Triple Helix Distribution

Distribution over sectors

Gender distribution

Figure 6: Graphical overview of the interviewees' characteristics

Funded by the European Union, through its Horizon Europe Program, Grant No. 101056957 (PREP4BLUE). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or of the granting authority, the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

8.2 Agenda Focus group workshop

PREP4BLUE

METHODS AND TOOLS FOR MISSION OCEAN & WATERS

Date: April 22, 2024
Time: 10:00 CET
Facilitator: Flanders Marine Institute (VLIZ)
 Toon Boydens, Chantal Martens, Matthias Sandra

AGENDA

TIME	ITEM	DESCRIPTION
10:00 – 10:15	Welcome and introduction	An overview of the workshop objectives will be given as well as an introduction to Mission Ocean and the Innovation Actions.
10:15 – 10:45	Mission Ocean Technological Solutions + Q&A	Testimonials will be presented by Innovation Actions, highlighting the technologies under development and the intended testing locations, as well as the barriers and enablers encountered in this process.
10:45 – 11:30	Policy and Regulatory Landscape + Q&A	Concrete examples of regionally focused regulatory landscapes associated with Mission Ocean will be presented and discussed. This will be supplemented by a presentation showcasing the results of policy mapping, identification of key obstacles, and the proposed solutions.
11:30 – 12:15	Collaborative Session: Building solutions and recommendations	Expanding on the earlier discussions and leveraging the groundwork laid in Prep4Blue, a collaborative session will be held for participants to delve into the proposed solutions, evaluating their feasibility and making additional contributions to bolster regulatory incentives. Drawing from their own experiences, participants will be able to address obstacles encountered, fostering a collaborative effort towards overcoming challenges
12:15 – 12:30	Final input and closing	Sharing of key insights and detailing the way forward

Figure 7: Agenda Focus group workshop

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8.3 Keywords for policy heatmap

- Protect and restore marine and freshwater ecosystems and biodiversity: ecosystem, biodiversity
 - Increased population of fish/molluscs/etc in Danube: fish stock, fish population, fish, fisheries
 - Innovation to counteract marine biodiversity loss (shipping, fishery, invasive species, nursery habitats): innovation, marine, biodiversity loss

- Prevent and eliminate pollution of our ocean, seas and waters: pollution
 - Upstream prevention of litter by design/chemical pollutants: river, litter, chemicals, pollutants, freshwater
 - Circular design of fishing gear: fishing gear

- Make sustainable Blue Economy carbon neutral and circular: blue economy, carbon neutral, circular, sustainable economy
 - Bringing algae-based products to the market: food, feed, waste, materials, textiles, pharma: algae, alternative protein
 - Mussel and seaweed aquaculture within OWFs and IMT: aquaculture, mussel, seaweed

8.4 Policy Heatmap

Table 2: Policy Heatmap

	has no clear link to the objective/topic
	has a clear link to the objective/topic

		Specific objective	Protect and restore marine and freshwater ecosystems and biodiversity (Danube & Atlantic-Arctic)			Prevent and eliminate pollution of our ocean, seas and waters (Med)			Make sustainable Blue Economy carbon neutral and circular (BANOS)		
EUROPEAN LEGISLATION	NAME	DESCRIPTION	GENERAL OBJECTIVE	Increased population of fish/mollusks/etc. in Danube	Innovation to counteract marine biodiversity loss	GENERAL OBJECTIVE	Upstream prevention of litter/chemical pollutants	Circular design of fishing gear	GENERAL OBJECTIVE	Bringing Algae based products to the market	Mussel and seaweed aquaculture within OWFs and IMT
Recommendation	Recommendation on integrated coastal zone management	2002/413 - Implementation of Integrated Coastal Zone Management in Europe	I.a								
Communication	Erika I	COM(2000) 142 final - Communication to Parliament and the Council on the safety of the seaborne oil trade (Erika I)				Introduction: Art. 8					
	Erika II										

	COM (2000) 802: Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament and the Council on a second set of community measures on maritime safety following the sinking of the oil tanker Erika									
Erika III	COM (2005) 585: Communication from the Commission - Third package of legislative measures on maritime safety in the European Union									
Integrated maritime policy	COM (2007) 575: Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions - An Integrated Maritime Policy for the European Union	4.1. Maximising the Sustainable Use of the Oceans and Seas		4.4. Promoting Europe's Leadership in International Maritime Affairs	1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY			2. Context		2. Context
Strategy for marine research	COM (2008) 534: Communication from the Commission to the Council, the European Parliament, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions - A European strategy for Marine and Maritime Research: A coherent European Research Area Framework in support of a sustainable use of oceans and seas	1. Introduction		1. Introduction						

Offshore Wind Energy	COM(2008) 768: Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions - Offshore Wind Energy: Action needed to deliver on the Energy Policy Objectives for 2020 and beyond	1. Offshore wind energy - A sea of unexploited opportunities		3.3. Maximising the environmental benefits of offshore wind				3.1. Investing in the future competitiveness of the EU wind energy industry		
Marine knowledge 2020	COM (2010) 461: Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament and the Council - Marine Knowledge 2020 marine data and observation for smart and sustainable growth	1. Context						3. Objectives		
Blue growth	COM (2012) 494: Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions - Blue Growth opportunities for marine and maritime sustainable growth	5.4. Marine mineral resources		1. Introduction	2. What is the Blue Economy ?			5. Blue Growth focus areas	5.5. Blue biotechnology	5.2. Aquaculture
Sustainable development in aquaculture	COM (2013) 229: Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions - Strategic guidelines for the sustainable development of EU aquaculture	3.2. Securing sustainable development and growth of aquaculture through coordinated spatial planning		3.2. Securing sustainable development and growth of aquaculture through coordinated spatial planning				3.3. Enhancing the competitiveness of EU aquaculture		3. Strategic guidelines for the sustainable development of EU aquaculture

Blue energy	COM (2014) 8: Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions - Blue Energy Action needed to deliver on the potential of ocean energy in European seas and oceans by 2020 and beyond	4. Challenges remaining		3. Existing Support				1. Contribution to employment, innovation, climate and energy objectives		
Maritime tourism	COM (2014) 86: Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions - A European strategy for more growth and jobs in coastal and maritime tourism							1. Introduction		
Innovation in the blue economy	COM (2014) 254: Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions - Innovation in the blue economy: realising the potential of our seas and oceans for jobs and growth	1. Introduction						2. Marine knowledge and seabed mapping		3. A marine research information platform
The European Green Deal	COM (2019) 640: Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the European Council, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions - The European Green Deal	2.1.7. Preserving and restoring ecosystems and biodiversity		3. The EU as a global leader	2.1.8. A zero pollution ambition for a toxic-free environment	2.1.8. A zero pollution ambition for a toxic-free environment		2.1.3. Mobilising industry for a clean and circular economy	2.1.6. From 'Farm to Fork': designing a fair, healthy and environmentally-friendly	

									food system	
EU Skills Agenda	COM (2020) 274: Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the European Council, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions - European Skills Agenda for sustainable competitiveness, social fairness and resilience	Introduction							2.5. Skills to accompany the green and digital transitions in jobs and beyond	
Biodiversity Strategy for 2030	COM(2020) 380: Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions - EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030	1. Biodiversity - The need for urgent action	2.2.6. Restoring the good environmental status of marine ecosystems	2.2.6. Restoring the good environmental status of marine ecosystems	2.2.9. Reducing pollution	2.2.9. Reducing pollution	2.2.6. Restoring the good environmental status of marine ecosystems	2.2.9. Reducing pollution		
Farm to Fork Strategy	COM(2020) 381: Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions - A Farm to Fork Strategy for a fair, healthy and environmentally-friendly food system	4. Promoting the global transition		2.2. Ensuring food security	2.1. Ensuring sustainable food production	2.1. Ensuring sustainable food production		2.1. Ensuring sustainable food production	2.1. Ensuring sustainable food production	2.1. Ensuring sustainable food production

new Circular Economy Action Plan	COM(2020) 98: Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions - A new Circular Economy Action Plan for a Cleaner and More Competitive Europe	6.1. Circularit y as a prerequisite for climate neutrality			3.4. Plastics			6.1. Circularit y as a prerequisite for climate neutrality		
Offshore Renewables	COM (2020) 273: Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions - An EU Strategy to harness the potential of offshore renewable energy for a climate neutral future	4.1 Maritime spatial planning for sustainable management of space and resources			1. Offshore Renewable energy for a climate-neutral Europe			3. EU's Sea Basins: A vast and varied potential to deploy offshore renewables	1. Offshore Renewable energy for a climate-neutral Europe 4.5 Focusing research and innovation on supporting offshore projects	4.1 Maritime spatial planning for sustainable management of space and resources
Strategic guidelines for a more sustainable and competitive EU aquaculture for the period 2021 to 2030	COM(2021) 236 Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions - Strategic guidelines for a more sustainable and competitive EU aquaculture for the period 2021 to 2030.	2.2.1. Environmental performance		2.2. Participating in the green transition	1. The need for a new EU strategy for aquaculture			1. The need for a new EU strategy for aquaculture	2. The new strategic guidelines	1. The need for a new EU strategy for aquaculture

new approach for a sustainable blue economy in the EU	COM(2021) 240: Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions - on a new approach for a sustainable blue economy in the EU Transforming the EU's Blue Economy for a Sustainable Future	3.1 Ocean knowledge		2.3 Biodiversity and investing in nature	2.2 Circular economy and preventing waste		2.2 Circular economy and preventing waste	1. Making the transition from 'Blue Growth' to a 'Sustainable Economy'	2.5 Responsible food systems	2.5 Responsible food systems
Zero Pollution Action Plan	COM (2021) 400: Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Region - Pathway to a Healthy Planet for All <i>EU Action Plan: 'Towards Zero Pollution for Air, Water and Soil'</i>	2.1 The zero pollution ambition		2.3 Living within our planetary boundaries - Link to MSFD	2.3 Living within our planetary boundaries	2.3 Living within our planetary boundaries		2.1 The zero pollution ambition		2.1 The zero pollution ambition
proposal for a Regulation on Ecodesign for Sustainable Products	COM(2022) 140: Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Region - On making sustainable products the norm	1. Introduction		1. Introduction	2. Our Ambition: Making sustainable products the norm.			1. Introduction		
Communication on Sustainable Algae Sector	COM(2022) 592 Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Region - Towards a Strong and Sustainable EU Algae Sector	1. Introduction		4.3. Close knowledge, data, technological and innovation gaps	1. Introduction			1. Introduction	1. Introduction	1. Introduction

State Aid for RDI	COM(2022) 7388: Communication from the Commission Framework for State aid for research and development and innovation 2022/C 414/01				Art. 137			Art. 5		
EU policy framework for biobased, biodegradable and compostable plastics	Communication COM(2022) 682 on EU policy framework on biobased, biodegradable and compostable plastics	3. Biobased plastics		4. Biodegradable and compostable plastics	1. Introduction	4. Biodegradable and compostable plastics	4. Biodegradable and compostable plastics	3. Biobased plastics		3.2 Feedstock sustainability
EU Hydrogen Strategy	COM/2020/301: A hydrogen strategy for a climate-neutral Europe	2. Towards a hydrogen ecosystem in Europe: A roadmap to 2050			1. Introduction			1. Introduction	6. Promoting R&I in hydrogen technologies	
Fit for 55	COM/20201/550: Fit for 55: delivering the EU'S 2030 Climate Target on the way to climate neutrality	1. 'Fit for 55': Delivering the EU's 2030 climate target on the way to climate neutrality			2.2 A competitive transition : New opportunities through industrial and sectoral change			2.2.1 Industrial transformation and carbon pricing		
AFIR	COM 2021/559: Proposal for a regulation on the deployment of alternative fuels infrastructure				1.1. Reasons for and objectives of the proposal			1.1. Reasons for and objectives of the proposal		

Directive	Nitrate Directive	COUNCIL DIRECTIVE 91/676/EEC - concerning the protection of waters against pollution caused by nitrates from agricultural sources	Introduction Art. 2			Introduction Art. 1	Art. 2 Art. 6				
	Habitat Directive	COUNCIL DIRECTIVE 92/43/EEC - on the conservation of natural habitats and of wild fauna and flora	Article 2	Article 12 Article 16 (b)	Article 12 (4)						
	Sulphur Directive	Directive (EU) 2016/802 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 May 2016 relating to a reduction in the sulphur content of certain liquid fuels (codification)	Introduction (34)			Introduction (5)					
	Directive on port reception facilities	Directive 2000/59/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 November 2000 on port reception facilities for ship-generated waste and cargo residues				Introduction (2) (3) (5) (6) (9)		Introduction (12)			
	Water Framework Directive	Directive 2000/60/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 October 2000 establishing a framework for Community action in the field of water policy	Art. 1 (a)			Introduction (40)	Introduction (7)				
	Directive on safe loading and unloading	Directive 2001/96/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 4 December 2001 establishing harmonised requirements and procedures for the safe loading and unloading of bulk carriers									
	Monitoring Directive	Directive 2002/59/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 June 2002 establishing a Community vessel traffic monitoring and information system and				Introduction (4) (6) (9)					

	repealing Council Directive 93/75/EEC									
Ship-Source Pollution Directive	Directive 2005/35/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 7 September 2005 on ship-source pollution and on the introduction of penalties, including criminal penalties, for pollution offences				Art. 1 (1)					
Port Security Directive	Directive 2005/65/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 26 October 2005 on enhancing port security									
Bathing Water Directive	Directive 2006/7/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 15 February 2006 concerning the management of bathing water quality and repealing Directive 76/160/EEC				Introduction (7)	Introduction (6)				
Directive on animal health requirements for aquaculture	Council Directive 2006/88/EC of 24 October 2006 on animal health requirements for aquaculture animals and products thereof, and on the prevention and control of certain diseases in aquatic animals						Introduction (6)		Introduction (4)	
Groundwater Directive	Directive 2006/118/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 December 2006 on the protection of groundwater against pollution and deterioration	Introduction (1) Art. 4			Introduction (6) Art. 3(1b)	Art. 3(2) Art. 4(4)				

Inspire Directive	Directive 2007/2/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 March 2007 establishing an infrastructure for spatial information in the European Community (Inspire)	Art. 1 (1)			Introductions (11)	Annex I (8.)				
Floods Directive	Directive 2007/60/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 October 2007 on the assessment and management of flood risks				Art. 6 (5(c))					
Marine Strategy Framework Directive	Directive 2008/56/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 June 2008 establishing a framework for community action in the field of marine environmental policy (Marine Strategy Framework Directive)	Introductions (18) Art. 3 (5.) - Annex 1	Art. 3 (5.) - Annex 1	Introductions (18)	introductions (19)	Annex III, Table 2				
Subsidiary Directive on priority substances	Directive 2008/105/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 2008 on environmental quality standards in the field of water policy, amending and subsequently repealing Council Directives 82/176/EEC, 83/513/EEC, 84/156/EEC, 84/491/EEC, 86/280/EEC and amending Directive 2000/60/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council	Introductions (1)	Art. 3 (2.)	Introductions (1)	Introductions (6)	Introductions (17)				
Seafarers' Training Level Directive	Directive 2008/106/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 November 2008 on the minimum level of training of seafarers (recast)									
Port State Control Directive	Directive 2009/16/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 April 2009 on port state control (recast)				Introductions (2) (4) (6)					

Birds Directive	Directive 2009/147/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 November 2009 on the conservation of wild birds	Introductions (2)			Art. 4. (4)					
Reporting Directive	Directive 2010/65/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 October 2010 on reporting formalities for ships arriving in and/or departing from ports of the Member States and repealing Directive 2002/6/EC									
Integrated Pollution Prevention and Control	Directive 2010/75/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 24 November 2010 on industrial emissions (integrated pollution prevention and control)				Art. 67	Art. 67				
Maritime Spatial Planning Directive	Directive 2014/89/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 July 2014 establishing a framework for maritime spatial planning	Introductions (1)		Introductions (13)				Introductions (3) (5)		Art. 8
Marine Equipment Directive	Directive 2014/90/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 July 2014 on marine equipment and repealing Council Directive 96/98/EC				Art. 1 Art. 8					
System of inspections for the safe operation of ro-ro passenger ships and high-speed passenger craft Directive	Directive (EU) 2017/2110 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 15 November 2017 on a system of inspections for the safe operation of ro-ro passenger ships and high-speed passenger craft in regular service and amending Directive 2009/16/EC and repealing Council Directive 1999/35/EC				Annex III (6)					

	Single Use Plastic Directive	Directive 2019/904/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 June 2019 on the reduction of the impact of certain plastic products on the environment	Introduction (5)		Introduction (15)	Introduction (15)	Introduction (6)	Introduction (5)	Introduction (1)		
	Seafarers Training Directive	Directive (EU) 2022/993 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 8 June 2022 on the minimum level of training of seafarers				Introduction (2) Art. 15(e)					
	Environmental liability Directive	Directive 2004/35/CE on environmental liability with regard to the prevention and remedying of environmental damage	Introduction (1)		Introduction (1)	Art. 4	Annex III		Introduction (31)		
	Animal Welfare Directive	Directive 2010/63/EU on the protection of animals used for scientific purposes as amended by Regulation (EU) 2019/1010	Introduction (16)								
	Packaging and packaging waste Directive	Directive 94/62/EC on packaging and packaging waste							Introduction		
	Renewable Energy Directive	Directive 2009/28/EC on the promotion of the use of energy from renewable sources	Introduction (69) & (78)			Introduction (42)			Introduction (3)	Introduction (89)	Art. 2 (e)
	Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive	Directive (EU) 2022/2464 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 December 2022 amending Regulation (EU) No 537/2014, Directive 2004/109/EC, Directive 2006/43/EC and Directive 2013/34/EU, as regards corporate sustainability reporting	Introduction (1)		Introduction (11)	Introduction (48)			Introduction (48)		
Regulation	Ship and Port Security Regulation	REGULATION (EC) No 725/2004 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE									

	COUNCIL - on enhancing ship and port facility security									
Regulation on alien species in aquaculture	Council Regulation (EC) No 708/2007 of 11 June 2007 concerning use of alien and locally absent species in aquaculture	Introduction (3) Art. 4		Art. 4				Art. 1	Art. 2(3) - all aquaculture activities	Art. 2(3) - all aquaculture activities
Regulation on IUU fishing	Council Regulation (EC) No 1005/2008 of 29 September 2008 establishing a Community system to prevent, deter and eliminate illegal, unreported and unregulated fishing, amending Regulations (EEC) No 2847/93, (EC) No 1936/2001 and (EC) No 601/2004 and repealing Regulations (EC) No 1093/94 and (EC) No 1447/1999	Introduction (3)	Introduction (6)	Introduction (3)				Introduction (2) - Sustainable economic conditions		
Common Methodology for Marine Casualties and Incidents Regulation	Commission Regulation (EU) No 1286/2011 of 9 December 2011 adopting a common methodology for investigating marine casualties and incidents developed pursuant to Article 5(4) of Directive 2009/18/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council				Annex A.					
Regulation on double-hull tankers	Regulation (EU) No 530/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2012 on the accelerated phasing-in of double-hull or equivalent design requirements for single-hull oil tankers				Introduction (2) (12)					
Ship Recycling and Amending regulation	Regulation (EU) No 1257/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 November 2013 on ship recycling and amending				Introduction (7) Art. 10(4)					

	Regulation (EC) No 1013/2006 and Directive 2009/16/EC								
Common Fisheries Policy Regulation	Regulation (EU) No 1380/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 December 2013 on the common fisheries policy, amending Council Regulations (EC) No 1954/2003 and (EC) No 1224/2009 and repealing Council Regulations (EC) No 2371/2002 and (EC) No 639/2004 and Council Decision 2004/585/EC	Introduction (22)	Art. 2(2)	Art. 55				Art. 28 (2c)	Introduction (2)(4)
Regulation on invasive alien species	Regulation (EU) No 1143/2014 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 October 2014 on the prevention and management of the introduction and spread of invasive alien species	Introduction (2) (3)		Introduction (1) Art. 1	Introduction (26) (33) Art. 21 - Pollutor pays principle				
MRV System Regulation	Regulation (EU) 2015/757 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 29 April 2015 on the monitoring, reporting and verification of carbon dioxide emissions from maritime transport, and amending Directive 2009/16/EC						Introduction (13)		
Animal Health Law	Regulation (EU) No 2016/429 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 9 March 2016 on transmissible animal diseases and amending and repealing certain acts in the area of animal health ('Animal Health Law')	Introduction (3) (21) Art. 1 (2b)					Art. 2(a.i.)		Art. 2(a.i.)

European climate Law	Regulation (EU) No 2021/1119 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 June 2021 establishing the framework for achieving climate neutrality and amending Regulations (EC) No 401/2009 and (EU) 2018/1999 ('European Climate Law')	Introduction (23)		Introduction (3) (23)				Introduction (22)		
European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund	Regulation (EU) No 2021/1139 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 7 July 2021 establishing the European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund and amending Regulation (EU) 2017/1004	Introduction (20) (30) (37) Art. 8 (5i) Art 14 (1f)		Art. 25	Introduction (51)		Introduction (37) Art. 25(2a&b)	Introduction (12) (51)	Introduction (39) - <i>'farming of aquatic animals and plants for the production of food and other raw material.'</i>	Introduction (12) Art. 3(2)
Taxonomy Regulation	Regulation (EU) 2020/852 on the establishment of a framework to facilitate sustainable investment, and amending Regulation (EU) 2019/2088	Introduction (7)		Introduction (7)	Introduction (23)	Introduction (7)		Introduction (4)		
Natural Restoration Law	Regulation on nature restoration COM (2022) 304 FINAL	Introduction (3)	Introduction (6)	Introduction (53)	Introduction (20)	Introduction (8)				

	Food and Feed Law	Regulation (EU) 2017/625 on food and feed law, rules on animal health and welfare, plant health and plant protection products	Introduction (8)						Introduction (11)		Introduction (5)
Other	Implementing Decision DC-MAP	Commission Implementing Decision (EU) 2016/1251 of 12 July 2016 adopting a multiannual Union programme for the collection, management and use of data in the fisheries and aquaculture sectors for the period 2017-2019.	I(10)	I(10)					III(5)		III(6)
	Black Sea SRIA Implementation Plan	Implementation Plan for the Black Sea Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA)	A COMMON VISION FOR THE BLACK SEA	A COMMON VISION FOR THE BLACK SEA		A COMMON VISION FOR THE BLACK SEA	A COMMON VISION FOR THE BLACK SEA		THE STRATEGIC RESEARCH AND INNOVATION AGENDA		THE STRATEGIC RESEARCH AND INNOVATION AGENDA

<p>LOCAL LEGISLATION</p>	<p>Salvamare Law (Puglia)</p>	<p>The "Salvamare Law" (Law No. 60/2022 "Provisions for the recovery of waste at sea and in inland waters and for the promotion of the circular economy"), which came into force following the transposition of Directive 2019/883/EU, aims to contribute to the recovery of the marine, lake and river ecosystem as well as to promote the circular economy, by encouraging the recovery of accidentally fished waste and voluntarily collected waste. In addition, with a view to environmental sustainability, it aims to encourage voluntary campaigns to clean up the sea and raise public awareness for the dissemination of virtuous behavioural models aimed at preventing the abandonment of waste in marine-coastal environments. Thanks to this law it will be possible now to start the waste collection in fishing ports of waste accidentally caught in the nets of fishing boats, preventing it from being thrown back into the sea because they are no longer considered special waste and therefore overtaxed.</p>									
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The Regional Strategy for Southwest Finland 2040+	The Regional Strategy for Southwest Finland 2040+ is also a key guiding document that indirectly contains the MO emphases, but it is not solely at the heart of the strategy. The regional strategy has been drawn up in extensive cooperation with various regional actors, and its implementation and monitoring are also carried out through regional partnerships.									
The Bremen hydrogen strategy					Positive: example of 'giving direction' (NOx restrictions)					
Burgas sustainable blue growth strategy								Positive: catalyse investments		
Valencian Climate Change and Energy Strategy 2030								Positive: catalyse investments		